

CORRELATION BETWEEN STANDARDIZED TEST & IQ

How does human intelligence quotient align with standardized test scores in the United States?

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Literature Review

Intelligence has been long debated for all of human history. As time has passed humans have gotten smarter and there was no way of measuring one's intelligence besides viewing their previous scholarly work or accomplishments. The IQ test, created in 1916 by a German psychologist named William Stern as an acronym for Intelligenz-Quotient (Hally 2015), was their first renowned test to measure intellect. It was speculated whether the test could actually gather a perspective on one's intelligence at first. The test was created in the early 1900's to gauge a student's ability to perform in school, which is very similar to standardized tests today. This would assume that test in the United States that are standardized such as the SAT and ACT which are used to gauge as a "college entrance examination" (College board 2024). So that begs the question: How does IQ align with standardized test scores in the United States? This would help to determine whether standardized test scores really represent a student's intelligence.

Created as a means of determining future education performance, the IQ test measures practical matters such as attention, memory and problem solving (Hally 2015) and also pattern recognition. The test is focused on not using subjects learned specifically in school. That is one key difference between the Standardized tests in the United States, which uses primarily topics covered in school, and the IQ test. The SAT and the ACT, however, do implement the tasks of problem solving and pattern recognition in the school-based topics tested. The IQ test has been implemented in numerous ways and has been scored differently in different time periods and different countries, although it has improved in quality drastically since its origin in the early 20th century and is now scored upon one's ability to solve problems and puzzles, as well as recognize patterns. The mean score of the modern IQ test in the United States is 98 (Cafasso 2018).

The average SAT score across the US is 1050 (Cheng 2023). Moreover, the average ACT score is 19 (Cheng 2023). The Scholars who created the IQ test and the SAT/ACT both strived to create a test similar to each other in purpose (to gauge further education readiness), but different in-depth content. Although it may seem counterintuitive to speculate on the correlation of these tests, the two should align due to their shared purpose. For example, A person with an IQ of 125 would be expected to have an SAT score of 1340 or an ACT score of 24. This may be expected to vary due to a usual margin of error of a few percent or the unquantifiable nature of a student's personal feelings towards standardized testing and its value, but overall should be aligned according to their purposes.

Most of the previous literature points toward a correlation between a few different factors in the case of both standardized test as well as IQ tests. A study done by Future Science Leaders points toward a positive correlation between family income and standardized test scores such as the SAT and ACT. Similarly, research done by Grey Enlightenment gives credence to the claim that income also correlates to IQ scores. Consequently, this shows a similarity in the correlation of the different tests and subsequent factors.

According to Stephen Murdoch in his book "A smart history of a failed idea, he explains how the IQ test when brought to the states was so profound and even transformed the idea of intelligence and what it is. The IQ test in the late 20th century when brought to the US was used in measuring intelligence of citizens for security reasons. The notion at that time was that people with a lower level of intelligence were substantially more likely to commit crimes. The IQ is now used mainly as a social gauge of relative intelligence due to the accessibility of these tests. IQ is measured using problem solving questions or simple puzzles along with pattern recognition. The tests are scored by using the number of correct responses paired with the time measured to complete the test.

Standardized tests, like the SAT and ACT emerged, as alternatives to IQ tests, aiming to provide a more comprehensive evaluation of students' academic abilities. These tests were designed to measure specific knowledge and skills taught in the modern school curriculum. These tests were not designed to merely measure intelligence, like IQ tests do, but instead to test on specific knowledge which is broad enough for the nation to take. However, like IQ tests, standardized testing has faced some backlash for their limitations such as socio-economic disparities in access to testing preparation and resources (W. Camara 2000).

In recent years, efforts have been made to address the limitations of both IQ tests and standardized tests. IQ tests have evolved to include a range of cognitive abilities that should be sufficient to determine a person's intelligence. They also have been created to minimize cultural and socio-economic biases and/or limitations. The newer IQ tests aim to provide an assessment that can be used across all diverse populations, reducing the impact if these biases on test performance (Reynolds 2008).

Similarly, standardized tests have undergone large revisions to improve the quality and fairness of the assessment. The SAT and ACT also aim to reduce cultural and socioeconomic biases (Camara 2000). This shows how standardized tests and tests to measure intelligence quotient have very similar surface value limitations that needed to be overcome. Tests like the ACT and SAT have been weighted heavily in the past during college admissions so there have been steps to ensure that standardized test scores don't play as large of a role. Nevertheless, the SAT and ACT still play a large role in one's college admissions. This shows the large amount of trust the universities and post-secondary education organizations put into these standardized tests. Despite these efforts, challenges remain in the use of IQ tests and standardized tests in education and psychology. Critics of these tests

argue that they oversimplify the complex nuances of the brain's capabilities and its detailed constructs like intelligence and academic achievement. Many state how the tests fail to capture the full range of human abilities and potential (Frey 2004).

Moreover, concerns persist about the influence of test scores on educational opportunities and societal perceptions. This reinforces inequalities rather than promoting equity and inclusion.

The majority of the current research surrounding scholarly conversation revolves around the effect of IQ testing and how accurate it is. Some research delves into the idea of how accurate an assessment of pure cognitive ability is. Others give a summary of the tests themselves and the history surrounding them. Furthermore, the same discussion has been dealt with in standardized testing: many of the articles and scholarly research done puts emphasis on the heavy weight on these tests and the ambivalent feelings toward the SAT and ACT due to not testing more than just skills and knowledge learned in the classroom.

IQ tests and standardized tests possess distinct characteristics in terms of the types of questions they offer. They reflect different purposes and methodologies. On one hand, IQ tests typically feature questions designed to assess cognitive abilities such as logical reasoning, pattern recognitions, and problem-solving skills. These questions often include sequences of numbers and patterns to answer a specific question. The tests often aim to gauge an individual's overall intellectual capacity and sometimes potential (Huang 2017). Often, IQ tests present participants with abstract visual patterns and require them to identify the missing piece discern the underlying rule which controls the sequence.

On the other hand, Standardized tests, like the ACT and SAT, encompass a larger range of subjects and overall educational skills. They reflect academic expertise and show proficiency in advanced concepts to show readiness for post-secondary education. These tests incorporate questions that cover a broad range of disciplines such as mathematics, reading, writing, and sometimes scientific concepts. Unlike the tests that measure intelligence quotient, the standardized tests include a range of question types as well: short answer, multiple choice, and essay prompts. They assess not just cognitive abilities, but also knowledge acquisition from numerous academic domains (Graham 2019).

Overall, IQ tests and standardized tests are different in content; although they serve a very similar purpose: to assess one's ability and intelligence overall. Even though they have their differences such as question types and the specific sector of content, the two tests do show similarities. In one's assessment of these two tests, they may be inclined to just to a conclusion of their correlation, but it is important to use real world facts and real human experiences to assess the true correlation and answer the question: How does human intelligence quotient align with standardized test scores in the United States?

Research and Analysis

The method used in this research was a survey method to collect data to then compile into a conclusion to the research question. This research method is mixed, being both quantifiable and quality based. The data collected was purely quantity based, being scores from SAT/ACT tests and IQ tests. On the other hand, the interpretation of the data was quality based because correlation can be interpreted as positive correlation, when two variables move in the same direction; negative

correlation, when two variables move in opposite directions; and zero correlation, no relationship between the two variables; with the research comprising one (or a combination of two) of the three correlation types.

Furthermore, based on statistics the best age group to research should be 16-45 years of age because they are the supposed prime of one's intellect and cognitive ability. One's ability in the intelligence sector can vary based on the specific person, with some peaking at 20 and some even at 40.

Therefore, by taking a margin on either end, the most viable age range of study participants can be formed. The exact test used for testing intelligence quotient consisted of an array of question types. Patterns of shapes, number sequences, and correlation of words were among the types of questions used in the IQ portion of the study.

Moreover, the test included 20 questions which calculated the score using the time one took on the test as well as the accuracy of the answers the tester provided. From the answers provided, a conclusion can be found using categories based on the correlation.

There is positive correlation, which means they correlate with one being high and the other also being high; negative correlation, where one is high and one is low; and no correlation where there is no correlation and no pattern. So, for this study, the categories will be: strong positive correlation, weak positive correlation, and no correlation. Strong positive correlation will be classified as a less than 5% difference in the scores divided by the average score for each, so for example, a score of 1080 (SAT) and a score of 100 (IQ) would be a 2.9% difference and therefore would be a strong positive correlation. On the other hand, weak positive correlation will be classified as between 5.01% and 20% and no correlation as 20.01% or higher

By acknowledging the previous scholarly research, the best hypothesis can be created: Standardized test scores and IQ scores will be positively correlated with little to no error. This is because of the previous scholarly research pointing towards the fact that the two tests, although different in content, were created to serve the same purpose.

By taking a survey of numerous participants from all over the United States, the numbers for the study on the correlation of standardized test scores and IQ are quite convincing. Specifically, 50% of all participants showed strong positive correlation between both their SAT or ACT score and their IQ score. This points towards a positive correlation, but it is important to review all the numbers and statistics before coming to a concise conclusion.

Many of the participants also showed a weak positive correlation as well. To be concise, 37.5% of all participants had a weak positive correlation. This leads to the last category of the study, which was “no correlation”. 12.5% of participants showed no correlation between the two scores. Overall, the demographic of participants was fair, 31.25% were women and 100% between the ages of 16-50.

The straightforward nature of the study is quite obvious and this allows for a very convincing conclusion. With precisely half of all the participants showing a strong positive correlation and another 37.5% showing a weak but still positive correlation, evidence points toward the conclusion of a clear correlation between IQ and standardized test scores. With the large majority of all participants showing some type of positive correlation and a small percentage of outliers, this points toward the most obvious conclusion: That IQ and SAT/ACT are correlated positively.

In this study, there could be numerous limitations that could have prevented the gathering of precise and accurate information. One example of a limitation is inaccurate test. By using social media

platforms and groups to gather participants, this could have led to rushed and therefore inaccurate IQ scores. Moreover, another example of a limitation could have been the age discrepancy. Along with the new age of technology, comes a new age of education. The average SAT score has risen with time and the standardized test score and its relative accuracy could be affected. Overall, the limitations have little effect on the broad goal and result of this study, but it is important to consider all factors in the study that lead to the final conclusion.

By including facts from past and present studies, a clear conclusion can be made. With the fact that the two tests are for the same purpose: The IQ test being used for future educational assessment and standardized tests are used for similar uses. The data that was recently collected also points toward the same conclusion. That is that standardized tests and IQ tests are correlated positively.

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